

Conditional constructions in Bàsàá (Bantu A 43)

Bàsàá is a Bantu A (43) language spoken in Cameroon with an estimated 300000 speakers (Lewis, Simons & Fennig 2016). The language enjoys a relative vitality with regard to the widespread language endangerment situation which characterizes many native languages spoken in Cameroon (Bitjaa 2007). Bàsàá is a lingua franca among neighboring groups such as Bakoko, Bati and Banen, at least among elderly generations of speakers who have lived continuously in the geographical settings of these ethnic languages.

Though the Bàsàá community is generally presented as a uniform speech group with only minor differences across dialects (Hyman 2003), this is not true throughout. While mutual intelligibility is evident between Bàsàá varieties spoken in the Nyong-et-Kelle Division and those present in the Sanaga-Maritime Division (Bikok, Babimbi 1 & 2, and Babimbi 3), mutual intelligibility is not naturally and thoroughly achieved between native speakers from Nyong-et-Kelle Division and those from the Nkam Division for example, as evidenced in the recently archived wordlists which had been collected within the framework of the ALCAM project.¹

The lumping together of all Bàsàá dialects into one allegedly unified language group has resulted from descriptions focusing on part of the dialectal continuum, namely the Nyong-et-Kelle and to a lesser extent Babimbi dialects. Perhaps because the two named varieties are native dialects to the first Bàsàá linguists who have produced early scholarly descriptive works on the language,² the remaining dialects are largely undescribed.

It should therefore be recalled that the present analysis of conditional constructions in Bàsàá is based solely on data stemming from the Nyong-et-Kelle and Sanaga Maritime varieties. However, this is not to infer that data and analyses presented here might not match the use of conditionals in other dialects. Indeed, it is very likely that other varieties might feature similar conditional patterns, but there might also be differences.

Conditional constructions are under-described in Bàsàá, as indeed is the case in most Bantu A languages. Even the comprehensive verbal system description of Bàsàá by Bitjaa Kody (1990) provides only a basic, arguably logical account of conditionals, against the backdrop of the French language conditional system. I will start by reviewing Bitjaa Kody's account of the conditionals in Bàsàá before sketching a typology and functional interpretation of these structures based on personal data³ as well as data from oral literature.

1. Review of Bitjaa Kody (1990)'s description of conditionals

Bitjaa Kody's (1990: 448-450) analysis of conditionals in Bàsàá focuses on the logical properties of conditional constructions and their morphosyntactic expression within the broader scope of tense marking as in (1), where P and Q stand for 'Supporting Clause' and 'Focal Clause' respectively.

- (1) a. [à jòp]P [m̀̀ m̀̀ -'pám]Q
3.SM COND.enter 1SG.SUBJ PRS.INCEP-go out
'If he comes in, I will go out/should he come in, I would go out.'

According to Bitjaa Kody (1990: 448), apart from the logical dependency of the subordinate clauses (protasis) on the main clause (apodosis), namely, for the latter to hold the former must be true, there exists a particular verb form which inflects the subordinate clause. This inflection is what Bitjaa Kody refers to as conditional. The verb form is an inflectional pattern which combines a zero morpheme and a floating high tone. In (1), the floating H combines with the verb base (*jòp* > *jòp* 'enter'), resulting in a contour HL tone.

Analysis of inflectional pattern in the apodosis is ignored in Bitjaa Kody's perspective, even in his subsequent examples shown in (2). The analysis in these examples only targets the 'if' clause (protasis), and Bitjaa Kody highlights a conditional morpheme which is marked by a floating H on the noun subject marker, and which spreads to the verb base, thereby triggering contour tone on underlyingly low tone monosyllabic verb bases, such as *lò* 'come'. However, it is not clear why Bitjaa Kody restricts the description of conditionals only to the protasis, when it is evident from the inflectional patterning that the conditional morpheme surfaces in both clauses. Indeed, the floating H morpheme is an spreads over through the apodosis. When the verb in the apodosis is monosyllabic with an underlying low tone root as with the verb *kàl* 'tell' in (2), the spreading H triggers a contour HL on the verb (*kàl* > *kàl*). Subsequently, the L mora in

¹ Part of the wordlists collected within the framework of the ALCAM (Atlas Linguistique du Cameroun) project are currently being digitized and archived with the Archive of Languages and Oral Resources of Africa (ALORA), and can be freely accessed via the following web link : <https://alora.cerdotola.com/ds/asv/?1>

² Such pioneer Bàsàá linguists include late Henry Marcel Bot Ba Njock through his seminal doctoral thesis *Nexus et nominaux en basaa* (1970), Pierre Lemb who has co-authored the first bilingual (Bàsàá/French) Dictionary in 1973 with François De Gastines, and Denis Zachée Bitjaa Kody (1990) in his doctoral thesis entitled "Le système verbal du basaa".

³ The author of the present paper happens to be a native speaker of Bàsàá from the Nyong-et-Kelle Division.

the contour HL may be upstepped to form a plateau with the adjacent right tone on the object complement *mê* ‘me’ (1SG personal pronoun) as a result of metatony (Makasso, 2012). However this upstepping does not occur if the verb is at the final position of the sentence as in (2e). Upstepping here is not therefore intrinsically related to conditional marking since; rather, upstepping is constrained syntactically, that is when the verb phrase in the apodosis has an object element.

It is also worth noting that polarity in tone pattern (LH vs HL) between two low-toned monosyllabic verbs (*lò* ‘come’, and *kàl* ‘tell’) in the protasis and the apodosis is due to polarity in information structure between the main clause and the conditional clause. Polarity in tone patterning here is aimed at balancing the information utterance in both clauses.

(2) a. *lò* ‘come’, *kàl* ‘tell’

[á lòó]P [ù káʼàl mē]Q
 1.SM.COND come.COND 2SG.SM COND.tell 3SG.OBJ
 ‘Should he/she come, tell it to me.’

b. *ɲó* drink

[á ʼɲó]P [ù káʼàl mē]Q
 1.SM.COND drink.COND 2SG.SM COND.tell 3SG.OBJ
 ‘Should he/she drink, tell it to me.’

c. *hèyà* take off

[á hèyá]P [ù káʼàl mē]Q
 1.SM.COND take off.COND 2SG.SM COND.tell 3SG.OBJ
 ‘Should he/she take off, tell it to me.’

d. *têdà* to keep

[á ʼtéédá⁴]P [ù káʼàl mē]Q
 1.SM.COND keep.COND 2SG.SM COND.tell 3SG.OBJ
 ‘Should he/she keep, tell it to me.’

e. [á lòó]P [ù kâl]Q
 1.SM.COND come.COND 2SG.SM COND.tell
 ‘Should he/she come, report it.’

One striking phenomenon here is the fact that this floating high tone causes a downstep on subsequent Hs, as is the case in (2.d), where the H mora of the contour tone in *têdà*⁵ is downstepped, whereas the L mora is raised to bear the same register as the preceding H.

2. Typology and functions of conditional constructions in Bàsàá

Conditionals in Bàsàá fall into two broad categories: Assertive and non-assertive conditionals. Assertive conditionals are genuine conditionals, which mirror a potential result likely to be achieved or fail. Assertive conditionals are those for which the condition is a pre-requisite for the achievement of a given result. Non-assertive conditionals do not project any tangible result even though they simulate conditionality.

2.1 Assertive conditionals. Assertive conditionals in Bàsàá can be said to be halfway between Longacre, Thompson and Hwang (2007)’s bipartite typology on the one hand, and Taylor (1997)’s tripartite model on the other hand; even though in their essence, both classifications models are described as complimentary (Steve Nicole in the present volume).

As in most languages, conditional constructions in Bàsàá generally consist in complex syntactic structures articulating a protasis (P) and an apodosis (Q). There is a canonical marker sequencing which underlies the use of conditionals in Bàsàá. On the one hand, the protasis is signaled by a generic conditional term *íbalé* ‘if’ (I later on refer to this term as ‘pivot marker’), which can be realized as *íbalé*, *íʼbalé* or *íbalé* depending on the type of condition being expressed. On the other hand, the apodosis is marked by the conditional morpheme *kî* (I later on refer to this term as

⁴ For the sake of lisibility, I have chosen to represent contour tones bearing units over two separate moraic segments when one of the tones mora is affected by either downstep or upstep.

⁵ For spelling convenience, contour tones in which one of the mora is subject to upstep or downstep are represented here on two segmental moras.

‘echo-marker) which stands in an echo-like position, since this marker cannot occur independently from its pivotal counterpart marker *íbalé*, whether the later is overt or implicit. I will therefore refer to this secondary term as an ‘echo conditional marker’, as opposed to its ‘pivot conditional marker’ counterpart.

Because of its potential to express specific condition patterns, the allomorph *íbalé* is to be distinguished from the two others which may be used interchangeably, at least in the Nyong-et-Kelle speech area.

The typology of conditionals in Bàsàá is highly constrained by the discourse framework. The propositional value of a given conditional sentence as reality vs unreality, factual vs hypothetical, or likely vs unlikely seems to be embedded in the discourse pattern of the speaker. In other words, assertive conditionality is mainly a function of the speaker’s perception of, or attitude towards some event bearing a prospective realization, whether past, present or future. One of the most visible consequences of context-dependent assertive conditional constructions in Bàsàá is the possibility of omitting both the pivot and echo conditional marker, as in (1) and (2). Omission of overt marking of conditionals is triggered, among other things, by the argument structure of discourse, that is, whether the argument being stated as a condition is newly introduced by the speaker, or has been introduced before, as shown in the following sentences.

- (3) a. [*íbalé* *ù* *m-bép* *mê*]P [*kí* *mè*⁶ *ń- ‘sáá* *wê*]Q
COND 2SG.SM PRS.PRF-beat 3SG.OBJ COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS.INCEP⁷-pay 3SG.OBJ
‘If you beat me, I will get even with you.’
- b. [*íbalé* *ù* *m-bép* *mê*]P [\emptyset *mè* *ń- ‘sáá* *wê*]Q
COND 2SG.SM PRS.PRF-beat 3SG.OBJ COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS.INCEP-pay 3SG.OBJ
‘If you beat me, I will get even with you.’
- c. [\emptyset *ù* *bép* *mê*]P [*kí* *mè* *ń- ‘sáá* *wê*]Q
COND 2SG.SM PRS.NARR-beat 3SG.OBJ COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS.INCEP-pay 3SG.OBJ
‘If you beat me, I will get even with you.’
- d. [\emptyset *ù* *bép* *mê*]P [\emptyset *mè* *ń- ‘sáá* *wê*]Q
COND 2SG.SM PRS.NARR-beat 3SG.OBJ COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS.INCEP-pay 3SG.OBJ
‘If you beat me, I will get even with you.’

While the logical content throughout the above examples remains identical, a morpho-syntactic modification is noticeable in (3c) and (3d), namely, the verb in the subordinate clause is inflected in the present narrative form. According to Bitjaa Kody (1990 : 439) corroborated by Hyman (2003), the past narrative form is used abundantly in narrative discourse in Bàsàá, and has the peculiarity of only occurring in complex syntactic constructions involving the presence of an initial clause where the verb is inflected in one of the perfective past tenses (P1⁸ P2 or P3). Assuming Bitjaa Kody’s descriptive stance, it should be understood in (3c) and (3d) that the use of the past narrative implies that the argument of the subordinate clause has already been introduced in the preceding discourse. This is to imply that the omission of a conditional marker is constrained by the frame of discourse as earlier stated, depending on whether the argument of the subordinate clause is topicalized or not.

It therefore follows that there may be isomorphy between conditionality and topicality in Bàsàá, as Haiman (1978) earlier mentioned it for Turkish and Tagalog. Isomorphy between conditionality and topicality in Bàsàá does not occur in absolute terms. While *íbalé* always triggers conditionality, it may occur in non-topical positions in the sentence as well.

The sentence in (3a) is unlikely to occur in actual speech production. The most obvious renderings here are those provided in (3b) and (3d). In other words, the conditional marker *kí* is not very much expected to appear in (3a). The most relevant explanation to this lies either in the speaker’s perception of the result of the condition being stated as certain, or in his attempt to make that result sound certain. At this juncture, it can be hypothesized that the presence or absence in discourse of the echo conditional marker *kí* is an indication to the factuality of the result stated in *Q*, on condition that *P* holds. This is shown further in (5) and (6) below.

As of the omission of *íbalé*, this is not dependent on either the condition or the result. Omission or requirement of *íbalé* relies solely on the information structure of the discourse. When the argument of the protasis has been introduced in a contiguous and preceding statement, and when that argument is being felt by both the speaker and the listener as still activated in the discourse memory, then *íbalé* may be omitted. Otherwise, when the argument is newly introduced or

⁶ The first singular subject marker *mè* I is articulated in spoken language as *mì* in the Nyong-and-Kelle speech area; e.g: *mì ñ’sáá wê* ‘I will pay you back/get even with you’. I am using the Sanaga-Maritime variant *mè* here for the sake of uniformity with available data in existing literature such as Bitjaa Kody (1990), where *mè* is used as the underlying form for the first singular subject marker.

⁷ The inceptive present tense in the main clause in (3a) and (3 b) can also be interpreted as a near future (F1) (Bitjaa Kody 1990:427).

⁸ Bitjaa Kody (1990)’s P1 (near past tense) is reinterpreted in the paper as present perfect.

when the speaker wants to state it afresh in a bit to bring it to the forefront of the discourse, *íḃá¹lé* performs both conditionality and topicalization.

For the sake of clarification, it would be useful to briefly recall that *íḃá¹lé* is morpho-syntactically analyzable as a topicalizing phrase, one which is describable as the combination of a topic marker *í* with a copula *ḃá* ‘be’, and to a subordinate marker *lé* ‘that’. The copula *ḃá* ‘be’ in this phrase appears in the past perfect⁹, which allows for a literal glossing of the topic phrase as ‘be it that’. More so, the structure of this topicalizing phrase allows for the insertion of additional pragmatic items such as the consecutive marker *ní*, as in (4).

- (4) *í* *ḃá* *ní* *lé*
TOP PST-PRF CONS REL
“Should it therefore be that.”

In natural speech production, the segmental topic *í* may not surface. In such cases, only a super H stands as the topic marker, and is therefore reported on the adjacent TBU to the right as in (2) above.

It follows from the above description of the pivot conditional marker *íḃá¹lé*, taken either as a phrase or lexeme that, being a topicalizing form, it is also a conditional where the expression of time plays a key role in locating the condition within a given point on the uncertain vs certain, factual vs non factual, likely vs unlikely continua. Let’s consider the following examples for illustration.

- (5) [*íḃá¹lé* *mè* *yí*]P [*kí* *mè* *ḃá* - *sómb* *má* - *làṅ*]Q
COND. 1SG.SUBJ PST-PRF.know COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS-PRF buy 8-oignon
“Had I known, I would had bought onions.”

- (6) [*íḃá¹lé* *mè* *ḃá* - *téhé* *má* - *làṅ*]P [(*kí*) *mè* *ḃá* - *sómb* *má* - *ò*]Q
COND. 1SG.SUBJ PRS-PRF 8-onion COND 1SG.SUBJ PRS-IPFV-buy 8-PRO
“If I see the onions, I would buy them.”

Both examples offer way to assessing the propositional value of expressed conditions through *íḃá¹lé* and *íḃá¹lé*, namely, with consideration to whether a given condition belongs to the positive or to the negative side of the conditionality continuum. In the first place, the structure in (5) does not allow omission of the echo conditional marker *kí*. Bearing this in mind, we can further point to the fact that verbs in the apodosis are in the past perfective form. Given that past perfective events are those whose realization is stated as completed, and mindful of the fact that the use of the echo marker *kí* is obligatory in this type of conditionals, it can be inferred that *kí* is the paramount marker of counterfactuality in Bàsàá conditions.

However, counterfactuality is also dependent on two additional parameters. First, we have the perfective aspect on the tensed verb in the protasis, which triggers the assumption that the realization of the condition though expected, has failed irreversibly. Second, the inflection of the topic marker in the topic phrase through a super H, which is responsible for subsequent H downsteps. When the super H spreads to the TBU of the copula, this results in *íḃá¹lé*, otherwise, the super H causes downstep on both the copula and the subordinate marker, thus resulting in *í¹ḃá¹lé*.

The super H in the pivot conditional marker signals hypothetical conditionality that is, uncertainty with regard to the realization of the condition stated in the protasis, as can be seen in (7) and (8). However, these types of conditional constructions require that the conditional marking slot in the apodosis be filled by the echo conditional marker *kí*.

- (7) [*íḃá¹lé* *à* *ḃá* - *téhé* *nyé*]P [(*kí*) *à* *ḃá* - *tí* *nyé* *kémbê*]Q
COND 1.SM PRS-PRF-see 3SG-OBJ COND 1.SM PRS-INCEP-give 3SG-OBJ goat
‘If he sees him/her, he would give her/him a goat.’

- (8) [*í¹ḃá¹lé* *à* *ḃá* - *téhé* *nyé*]P [(*kí*) *à* *ḃá¹tí* *nyé* *kémbê*]Q
COND 1.SM FUT.NEAR-see 3SG-OBJ COND 1.SM FUT.NEAR-give 3SG-OBJ goat
‘Should he see him/her, he would give him/her a goat.’

As has already been mentioned, the two alloforms *íḃá¹lé* and *í¹ḃá¹lé* are free variants, and they do not obligatorily require overt articulation of the echo-form, as the parentheses in (7) and (8) illustrate. The difference between hypothetical and counterfactual conditionals in Bàsàá resides in the former being introduced by the discontinued

⁹ Compare with present form *yè* as in *mè yè* ‘I am’.

conditional expression *íḃá¹lé/í¹ḃá¹lé ...kí*, where *kí* may be omitted, and the latter being introduced by *íḃá¹lékí*, without allowing the omission of *kí*.

Hypothetical conditions in Bàsàá are further characterized by either present or future tense marking on the inflected verbs in both the protasis and the apodosis.

It is safe to say that grammatical marking of hypothetical conditionals in Bàsàá is mainly done by prosody, and that it is manifested through a super H at the onset of the pivotal condition marker in the protasis. Consider examples (9) and (10) below.

- (9) [Màkàsò á lǎ]P [Báyíhā à yí-s mē]Q
 Makaso 1.SM.COND come.COND Bayiha 1.SM know-CAUS 1.SG.OBJ
 ‘Should Makasso come, let Bayiha inform me.’

- (10) [Hy - àngáá h - í bǎy]P [Mátip à pém - és kémbê]Q
 19 - sun 19-SM.COND shine.COND Matip 1.SM let out-CAUS sheep
 ‘Should the sun shine, let Matip let out the sheep.’

In the two preceding examples, the super H appears on the subject markers, *à* and *hí*. The tone associated with class 1 concord subject marker *à* is underlyingly L, whereas the one associated with class 19 concord subject marker *hí* is underlyingly H. This is illustrated in the following examples which are introduced by *íḃá¹lé*, in contrast with (9) and (10), where conditionality is solely expressed by a super H on the two class concord subject markers.

- (11) [í¹ḃá¹lé Màkàsò à n-lǎ]P [(kí) Báyíhā à n - ¹yí-s mē]q
 COND Makaso 1.AGR PRS.PRF-come COND Bayiha 1.SM PRS.INCEP-know-CAUS 1SG-OBJ
 ‘If Makasso comes, Bayiha would/will let me know.’

- (12) [í¹ḃá¹lé hy-àngáá h - í m - bǎy]P [Mátip à m - ¹pém - és ¹kémbê]Q
 COND 19 – sun 19-SM.COND PRS.PRF-shine Matip 1.SM PRS.INCEP- let out-CAUS sheep
 ‘‘If the sun shines, Matip would let out the sheep.’

In an attempt to acoustically reflect the difference in pitch between the two respective H in (10) and (12), I have self recorded these two utterances in a studio using standard recording parameters of 88.2kHz/16bits, linear PCM mode. The two utterances have been recorded in one file and continuously, with a gap of 2.427 seconds between the first and the second. The resulting sound file has been transcribed and acoustically analyzed using PRAAT. A synchronized picture of the wave form, pitch contour and texgrid for the two utterances have been drawn as shown in figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 represents the Wave form and pitch contour of the protasis *í¹ḃá¹lé hy-àngáá hí m-bǎy* in (12). Figure 2 is the Wave form and pitch contour of the protasis *Hy-àngáá hí bǎy* provided in (10).

Fig 1: Wave form and pitch contour of the protasis *í¹ḃá¹lé hy-àngáá hí m-bǎy* (12).

Fig 2: Wave form and pitch contour of the protasis *Hyàngáá hí bǎy* (10).

The acoustic analysis of the two utterances show an extra-rising of H on class 19 subject marker *hí-* in (10) as compared with (12). This testifies to the prosodic nature of conditionality marking with regard to hypothetical conditionals in *Bàsàá*

The super H is further replicated on the echo marker *kí* in the protasis, which is in additional support of the syntactic relatedness of the pivot and the echo markers on the one hand, and of prosodic prominence of conditionality marking.

From the point of view of their semantic and pragmatic interpretation, there is no real difference between hypothetical conditionals expressed through *í⁴bálé/í⁴bálé* on the one hand, and those expressed by means of a super H. However, omission of *í⁴bálé/í⁴bálé* and its replacement by a super H may be stressing the speaker's argumentative stance with regard to the outcome of the condition.

There is a third assertive conditional type in *Bàsàá*, which shares some characteristics with counterfactual conditionals on the one hand and hypothetical ones on the other. This third type can be labeled either as “factual” (Taylor 1997), or as “reality conditionals” (Longacre, Thompson and Hwang 2007). Factual or reality conditionals have a two-slotted condition marking distributed over the protasis and the apodosis. As with hypotheticals, the protasis in factual conditionals is introduced by the topic phrase *í⁴bálé/í⁴bálé*. However, the echo-form is represented by the epistemic marker *wě* ‘then’ in the apodosis. *wě* is used to state the certainty of the result if the condition holds.

- (13) [í⁴bálé ù bí - ⁴téhé túyê]P [wě ù bí - kè¹⁰ tóy í Kribì]Q
 COND 2SG.SM PST.NEAR-see sea EPIST 2SG.SM PST.NEAR-go EVID LOC Kribi
 ‘If you saw the sea, then you have obviously been to Kribi.’

- (14) [í⁴bálé à ò - jê - k bée]P [wě njàl ì gwě bée nyé]Q
 COND 3.SM PRS-PRF eat – not yet NEG EPIST 9.hunger 9.SM hold.STAT NEG 3SG.OBJ
 ‘If he has not yet eaten, therefore he must not be hungry.’

Factuality induced by the echo conditional marker *wě* is further evidenced by tense inflection in the protasis; namely, conditional constructions of the type *í⁴bálé/í⁴bálé ... wě* do not allow remote past/future verb inflection in the protasis, as these tenses are usually associated with unlikelihood, as in (15).

- (15) *[í⁴bálé ù téhé túyê]P [wě ù k ě tóy í Kribì]Q
 COND 2SG.SM PST.REMOTE.see sea ESPIST 2SG.SM PST.REMOTE.go EVID LOC Kribi

Example (15) is ruled out in ordinary language usage because there is a logical inadequacy between the unlikelihood of the condition laid down in the protasis and the factuality of the result stated in the apodosis.

¹⁰ Optionally, we may have the past perfect tense instead of the near past

(1) í⁴bálé ù bí - ⁴téhé túyê wě ù bē tóy í Kribi
 COND 2SG.SM PST.NEAR-see sea then 2SG.SM PST.STAT-go EVID LOC Kribi

Remote conditional events denoting unlikelihood can be more fittingly articulated by the *kí* marker in the protasis, in-so-far as *kí* is the prominent indicator of hypothetical conditions in Bàsàá. In the case of (15), conditionality has to be stated in the reverse order, thereby highlighting the unlikelihood of the condition.

(16) [íbálé ù ké tóy í Kribi]P [kí ù bí - 'téhé túyê]Q
 COND 2SG.SM go.PST.PRF EVID LOC Kribi COND 2SG.SM PST.NEAR-see see
 'If you had really been to Kribi, you would have seen the sea.'

(17) [íbálé ù bá há]P [kí m̀e bí - 'pód - ós wê]Q
 COND 2SG.SM be.PST.PRF DEICT COND 1SG.SUBJ PST.NEAR-talk-CAUS 1SG.OBJ
 'I would have talked to you, (if you) had (you) been there.'

Factuality does not always correspond to real world or historically attested events. Therefore, factual conditionals in Bàsàá can be used to express general truth; in such cases, they may bear a proverbial value as in (18).

(18) [(íbá'lé) ù gwě bì - tòn]P [wě ù gwě m̀o]Q
 COND 2SG PRS.STAT-have 8 - palm nut EPIST 2SG PRS.STAT-have 6.oil
 'He who possesses palm nuts equally possesses palm oil.'

Example (18) could have also been glossed as 'if you possess palm nuts, then you cannot lack oil'.

2.2 Non assertive conditionals. I also refer to assertive conditionals as “weak conditionals”, that is, those conditional constructions whose conditionality triggers a strong argumentative weight. They are neither meant to express prediction nor unlikelihood per se. Instead, the speaker uses the propositional biases of conditionality as irrealis, to achieve argumentative ends with regard to a specific topic or idea. Among non assertive conditionals, concessive ones have to be distinguished from rhetorical ones. Rhetorical conditionals as will be discussed in more details in 2.2.2, are more formulaic than propositional, in the sense that their interpretation is not derived from the logical dependency of an expected outcome, but rather capitalizes on the uncertainty of conditionality.

2.2.1 Concessive conditionals. Expression of concession through conditional constructions has been dealt with in earlier works (Hopper & Traugott 1993: 180; Thompson et al. 2007:261). This type of conditionals which in English may be introduced by *even if*, do not indeed express conditionality at all according to Nicole (in the present volume) following Lycan (2001), because they cannot receive an *iff* (“if and only if”) interpretation.

Concessive conditionals in Bàsàá have a slightly different interpretive potential. Not only are they likely to be embedded in the *íbálé ... kí* conditionality marker frame (20) and (22), but they can perfectly receive an *iff* interpretation. Both (19) and (20) for example may be paraphrased as ‘if and only if I could have helped it, the goat would not have been slaughtered’, just as (21) and (22) could well be reworded as ‘if and only if it were for his/her performance, she/he wouldn't have passed the exam’. The parenthesis in the above examples signals optional terms.

(19) [kí m̀e ḱi m̀e]P [kí kémbê ì ñ - nól - á b́eé]Q
 SGV 1SG [SGV 1SG]DUP COND 9.goat 9.SM PRS.PRF-kill - PASS NEG
 'If I could help it, the goat would not have been killed.'

(20) [íbálé ḱi m̀e (ḱi m̀e)]P [kí kémbê ì ñ - nól - á b́eé]Q
 COND SGV 1SG [SGV 1SG]DUP COND 9.goat 9.SM PRS.PRF-kill-PASS NEG
 'If I could help it, the goat would not have been killed.'

(21) [kí òlóló y - éé 'ḱi òlóló y - éé]P [kí à ñ - nê]Q
 SGV 7.work 7.AGR-POSS [SGV 7.work 7.AGR-work] DUP COND 1.SM PRS.PRF-pass

b́e má - k̀èksè]Q

NEG 6-exam

'Had it only been for her/his performance, she/he would not have passed the exam.'

(22) [íbálé kì òlò y - éé '([kì òlò y - éé)]P [kí à ò - nê
COND SGV 7.work 7-POSS [SGV 7.work 7 – POSS]DUP) COND 1.SM PRS.PRF-pass

óé má - kèksè]Q

NEG 6-exam

'Had it only been for her/his performance, she/he would not have passed the exam.'

As the parentheses suggest, the pivot conditional marker *íbálé* may be used in the protasis as in (19) and (21), or omitted as in (20) and (21). However, the echo condition marker *kí* is obligatory. This syntactic-semantic layout of concessive conditionals would have qualified them to be classified among assertive conditionals. The reality however, is that these conditionals do not project a prospective result, likely or unlikely to occur. Rather concessive conditionals are used argumentatively to bias a proposition towards its unreality end. In short, on the basis of their semantic potentials, concessive conditionals are to be considered as genuine conditionals in Bàsàá. From the point of view of their pragmatic motivation however, these conditionals qualify as non-asserted.

In any case, the singulative marker *kì* is to be derived from, or equated with the echo marker *kí*; both have distinct meanings and functions.

In addition to serving argumentative ends, concessive conditionals may be used as stylistic devices. This occurs in cases of syntactic reduplication as in (19) and (21), but also in balanced negative vs positive protasis as in (23).

(23) [ù téédá ŋw - áá w - ôŋ njòm y - òŋ]P
2SG.SM PRS.NARR.COND-care for¹¹ 1 – wife 1.AGR-POSS 9.issue¹² 9-POSS

'Whether you care for your wife is up to you'

[ù téédá óé nyé njòm y - òŋ]Q'
2SG PRS.NARR.COND-care for NEG 3SG.OBJ 9.issue 9 – POSS

'Whether you do not care for her is up to you (as well)'.¹²

2.2.2 Rhetorical conditionals. Rhetorical conditionals implicitly express a negative assertion against the propositional content of the condition being stated in the protasis.

(24) [Màkàsò á lǎ - k lèn]P [ù hé'yá 'mê j - òy]Q
Makasso 3.SM.COND come.COND-IRR today 2SG.SM remove.PST.NARR 1SG.OBJ 5 – name
'Should Makasso come today, don't call me by my name anymore'

(25) [íbá'lé Màkàsò à ò - ló lèn]Q [ù hé'yá 'mê j - òy]Q
COND Makasso 3.SM PRS.PRF- come today 2SG.SM remove. PST.NARR 1SG.OBJ 5 – name
Should Makasso come today, don't call me by my name anymore'

Rhetorical conditionals do not require the use of *íbálé* 'if' in the protasis, though, in certain circumstances, this pivotal marker may surface as in (25). Unlike the pivot conditional marker which may be optionally omitted in the protasis, no echo marker is allowed in the apodosis, either *kí* or *wě*.

The use of *íbálé* alongside the irrealis marker '-Vk' is aimed at achieving specific pragmatic ends, namely that of providing advice, warning, injunction, or negative prediction, given the unlikely occurrence of a given condition.

3. Summary of findings and conclusion

Two broad categories of conditionals have been identified in Bàsàá, namely assertive conditionals and non-assertive conditionals. Assertive conditionals have been further classified in three sub-types: counterfactuals, hypothetical, and factual or reality conditionals. Non assertive conditionals in Bàsàá consist of two sub-types: concessive and rhetorical conditionals.

The above description of conditional constructions in Bàsàá is more tentative than definitive. The limitation of the analysis is both constrained by the scope of the data used and the non-representativeness of the overall Bàsàá speech area. Moreover, the methodology used in gathering the data, that is from a native speaker's intuition and oral literature,

¹¹ An alternative glossing is 'keep'.

¹² Alternative glossing : 'matter', 'problem'.

do not provide a comprehensive account of all possible conditional forms. For all these reasons and perhaps others, the analysis of conditionals in Bàsàá as proposed in this paper should be considered a work in progress.

Abbreviations

∅	Zero morpheme	IPFV	Imperfective
1SG	1 st person singular	IRR	Irrealis
2SG	2 nd person singular	ITER	Iterative
3SG	3 rd person singular	LOC	Locative
1	Noun class one	NARR	Narrative
2	Noun class two	NEAR	e.g. Near past, near future
3	Noun class three	NEG	Negative
6	Noun class six	OBJ	Object
7	Noun class seven	PI	Near past
8	Noun class eight	PASS	Passive
9	Noun class nine	POSS	Possessive
19	Noun class nineteen	PRF	Perfective
AGR	Agreement	PRO	Personal pronoun
CAUS	Causative	PRS	Present
COND	Conditional	PST	Past
CONS	Consecutive	REL	Relative
DEICT	Deictic	Remote	e.g. Remote past, remote future
DEM	Demonstrative	SG	Singular
DUP	Duplicate	SGV	Singulative
EQUA	Equative	SM	Subject Marker
EPIST	Epistemic	STAT	Stative
EVID	Evidential	SUBJ	Subjet
INCP	Inceptive	TOP	Topicalizer

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